

Assessment of Tube Voltage and Current-Time Product in Digital Mammography: Effects on Image Quality Parameters

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Abstract— This study evaluated tube voltage and current-time product in digital mammography, analyzing their effects on image quality. A Piranha 657 multiparametric meter and a breast phantom were used. The accuracy and reproducibility of tube voltage were evaluated to ensure that the equipment operated within voltage limits. Quantitative analysis of image quality used MATLAB to calculate the mean, standard deviation, signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), and structural similarity index (SSIM) for images acquired at 33 kV and 35 kV. The results indicated that a 6.06% increase in tube voltage did not cause significant variations in the mean, standard deviation, or SNR. The accuracy and reproducibility tests were considered satisfactory, meeting the requirements of IN 92. The study concluded that quality control is crucial for image safety and quality, and that increasing the tube voltage, even within regulatory limits, did not significantly improve image quality and increased the radiation dose. Computational methods such as SNR and SSIM provide a valuable quantitative approach to radiological practice.

Keywords— Image Quality, Mammography, Radiological Protection, Quality Control, Tube Voltage.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cancer comprises a group of over 100 diseases marked by uncontrolled and abnormal cell growth, often resulting in tumors that can metastasize to other parts of the body. These cells tend to be aggressive and proliferate uncontrollably. They cause the formation of tumors, which can spread to other parts of the body.

Breast Cancer is the most prevalent types among women worldwide, with high mortality rates particularly among

Brazilian woman aged 40 to 69. Early diagnosis is essential to reducing mortality in these women. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), mammography is the most effective and least invasive method for detecting disease (WHO, 2014).

High-resolution image quality is a determining factor in ensuring reliable diagnoses, allowing for better visualization of lesions and structures that are difficult to identify, such as microcalcifications. Therefore, there is a need for control and attention to technical parameters of use to avoid errors that compromise this quality and prevent diagnostic errors with false negatives and positives (Corrêa et al., 2012).

Rigorous and continuous checks, including periodic tests, are essential to ensure that the equipment meets the required standards and safety requirements (INCA, 2019).

Normative Instruction No. 092 and Resolution RDC No. 611/22 are essential for establishing technical requirements for the operation and maintenance of equipment. They establish dose limits, training and maintenance standards, as well as health requirements to ensure the quality and safety of mammography systems (IN No. 92).

These measures ensure that image quality is maintained, preserving the health of all those involved in radiodiagnostic processes to the maximum extent possible (ANVISA, 2022).

The use of radiation detectors to monitor parameters such as doses, exposure time, voltage applied to X-ray tubes, and air kerma rate ensures image quality (Neto et al., 2024).

Ionizing radiation exposed in mammography exams in Brazil must be regulated by standards established by the National Nuclear Energy Commission (CNEN) and the National Health Agency (ANVISA) to prevent harm to the

life of the patient undergoing the exam and to the professional performing the exam, in addition to balancing the obtaining of high-quality images with low radiation doses (Tanimoto Sarau et al., n.d.).

Radiological protection in mammography adheres to the ALARA (As Low As Reasonably Achievable) principle, which aims to minimize radiation exposure without compromising image quality. This ensures safe and efficient examinations for both patients and professionals, supporting accurate diagnostic outcomes, which seeks to reduce radiation exposure to the lowest possible level so that the quality of image formation is not compromised and to ensure that mammography exams are performed safely and efficiently for the safety of patients and professionals and to ensure accurate diagnoses (INCA, 2019).

Quality control in mammography ensures accurate, standardized diagnoses and is directly linked to radiation protection and safety. Its importance extends beyond more equipment maintenance.

II. METHODS

This study conducted quality control tests on digital mammography (DR) equipment, following the Medical Radiodiagnostic Guide and Normative Instruction No. 92 (ANVISA, 2021). Data collection took place at a Health Care Facility in Uberlândia, Minas Gerais, Brazil, in 2024.

The mammography unit used was a Mammomat Fusion VB 60F (Siemens). Measurements were captured using Ocean software in conjunction with the Piranha 657 multiparametric meter, version 5.5 (RTI Electronics). This device utilizes its internal detector to provide data such as tube voltage, exposure time, dose, dose rate, half-value layer (HVL), and air kerma. Additionally, the Cleopatra Phantom, a breast simulator, was used for image acquisition (PINHEIRO, 2024).

A. Image acquisition

The Cleopatra breast simulator was used to evaluate image quality and breast tissue representation (PINHEIRO, 2024). Image capture followed the 150 N breast compression protocol established by Normative Instruction No. 92 (ANVISA, 2021). Images were acquired voltages of 33 kV and 35 kV. The latter being the maximum limit allowed according to the height of the compressed simulator's height (45 mm). Thus, it was possible to quantify the effect of this 6.06% increase in tube voltage.

B. Acquisition with Multiparametric Meter

In this study, tests were conducted to verify the accuracy and reproducibility of the tube voltage, ensuring that the equipment operated within specified voltage limits. This is crucial as tube voltage directly influences image quality and the patient's radiation dose.

1. Tube Voltage Accuracy and Reproducibility Test

To check how accurate and repeatable the X-ray tube voltage is, the test was adapted to a single kV value using the Piranha multiparametric meter and followed the methodology and calculations performed in Excel.

- The meter was positioned on the breast support centered with the equipment's guide light 4 cm from the chest wall;
- The most commonly used nominal voltage value clinically was set;
- Five mAs values, corresponding to those used in the mammography simulator images, were set;
- Three exposures were performed for each defined mAs value.

The accuracy of the values was calculated by the deviation (d), using the average tube voltage values (KVmed) and the nominal voltage (KVnom), as seen in Equation (1) below:

$$d(\%) = 100 \cdot \frac{KV_{nom} - KV_{med}}{KV_{nom}} \quad (1)$$

The coefficient of variation (CV) was calculated using the standard deviation (σ) and the mean voltage values (KVmed), as shown in Equation (2):

$$CV = 100 \cdot \frac{\sigma}{KV_{med}} \quad (2)$$

Based on Equations 1 and 2, the expected values for d and CV were $d \pm 5\%$ and $CV \leq 2\%$, respectively.

C. Quantitative Analysis of Digital Image Quality

The quality of mammographic images was assessed using MATLAB software for image analysis and processing. The objective of this step was to quantify quality parameters such as mean, standard deviation, SNR, SSIM, and similarity between two identical images with different tube voltages and noise levels.

1. Mean and Standard Deviation

To evaluate the quality of the Cleopatra Phantom images, the mean and standard deviation were calculated for images acquired at 33 kV and 35 kV using MATLAB software

The average intensity values of each pixel can be used to quantify image brightness. Thus, the difference in brightness caused by the 6.06% increase in tube voltage was analyzed. The formula is presented in Equation (3):

$$\mu_x = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i \quad (3)$$

Where N is the total number of pixels and x_i is the intensity value of the i th pixel.

The standard deviation was used to analyze the dispersion of pixel intensity values around the mean, and to observe the increase or decrease in noise as a function of the increased kV.

Equation (4) represents the mathematical formula for standard deviation:

$$\sigma_x = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu_x)^2} \quad (4)$$

The standard deviation can also indicate the amount of contrast in the image; the greater the contrast, the greater the standard deviation, indicating a large variation between pixel intensities.

2. Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) and Structural Similarity Index (SSIM)

The Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) was used to analyze whether the noise level increased with the increase in tube voltage. SNR measures image quality by comparing the ratio between the signal and unwanted noise. In MATLAB, the signal-to-noise ratio was used according to Equation (5):

$$SNR = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \frac{Mean^2}{Standard\ deviation^2} \quad (5)$$

This equation is a specific way of calculating Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) in image processing, where "signal" and "noise" are defined in a particular way. The grayscale average is a measure that represents the signal in the image.

The standard deviation is a measure of noise, this value represents the level of random noise present in the image. Squaring the mean (signal) and the standard deviation (noise) and dividing the former by the latter results in a simple ratio. To convert this measurement to dB, $10 \cdot \log$ is applied to this ratio to obtain the final signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) in decibels.

A higher SNR indicates a better quality image, while a low SNR indicates that the noise is close in intensity to the signal, making it difficult to identify details (Mudeng et al., 2022).

The Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) was used to evaluate the difference between the images generated with tube voltage, assessing how the different tube voltage influenced the images (Mudeng et al., 2022). The MATLAB algorithm considers three components: luminance, contrast, and structure, as seen in Figure 1, which provide a score between 0 and 1, with 1 being the maximum similarity between images and 0 the minimum similarity.

Fig. 1 Structural Similarity Index

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A preliminary visual analysis of the images acquired from the breast simulator did not reveal any major differences. There was a 6.06% increase in tube voltage, from 33 kV to 35 kV, used in conjunction with the mAs control automatically selected by the mammography machine based on breast thickness and compression.

The automatic adjustment of mAs allowed the exposure to be adapted according to individual anatomical characteristics, ensuring an optimized radiation dose and adequate image quality for each patient. This variation in voltage and current-time product certainly produces different images, especially in contrast and brightness. Therefore, there is a need to analyze and quantify the effects of variation on the image.

The quality control tests performed with the Piranha multiparametric meter obtained several parameters (tube voltage, exposure time, exposure, exposure rate, mAs, semi-reducing layer, among others). However, as this study analyzes the effects of increased tube voltage on the image, only the tube voltage values and other values necessary to calculate accuracy and reproducibility were used.

A. Test of accuracy and reproducibility of tube voltage

Table 1 presents the data acquired with the meter and the calculations performed to analyze the accuracy of the tube

voltage. The tube voltage configured in the mammography equipment was 33 kV. The mAs values were differentiated to see the proportionality of the increase according to the dose and the mama compression. The mAs values were chosen according to the analysis of the DICOM information from the breast simulator images and what each of them received from the current time product in automatic exposure mode. The mean and deviation (d) were calculated, indicating the percentage of accuracy error.

Table 1 – Calculations of kV values, averages, and deviation (d).

mAs	Average tube voltage (kV)	Deviation ($\pm 5\%$)
14	32.779	0.667
20	32.673	0.989
25	32.699	0.909
40	32.668	1.003
56	32.646	1.072

With the deviation calculus, we can analyze that the accuracy of the tube voltage is, in fact, within the requirements of IN 92, a value of $\pm 5\%$.

The results of the tube voltage reproducibility test followed the same parameters as the accuracy test and can be seen in Table 2. The standard deviation and coefficient of variation were calculated using Excel according to Equation (2), which indicates the consistency of the reproduction of X-ray tube shots.

Table 2 Calculus of standard deviation and coefficient of variation (CV)

mAs	Average tube voltage (kV)	Standard Deviation (σ)	CV ($\leq 2\%$)
14	32.779	0.667	0.190
20	32.673	0.989	0.095
25	32.699	0.909	0.113
40	32.668	1.003	0.158
56	32.646	1.072	0.072

The reproducibility results are satisfactory, adhering to IN 92 requirements, with CV values less than or equal to 2%. Regular testing of these parameters is crucial to ensure that the mammography machine functions as expected and maintains the radiological safety of patients. Thus, quality control contributes to the early detection of equipment failures and necessary adjustments, promoting safer exams and high-quality images.

B. Quantitative Analysis of Digital Image Quality

The computational results of this article were done utilizing Microsoft Excel and MATLAB Software. Table 3 shows the results of the calculations performed on the images

acquired from the mammography simulator. The calculation of mean and standard deviation are important for the objective interpretation of the acquired images with different kV (33 and 35). So, they can be applied in the calculation of the SNR metric.

Table 3 Mean and Standard deviation calculations of the images and your respective mAs values

Figure	mAs	Mean (kV)		Standard Deviation	
		33 kV	35 kV	33 kV	35 kV
A	14	10.39	10.24	29.4	28.81
B	20	14.05	13.88	43.44	43.09
C	25	10.66	10.59	30.77	30.39
D	40	14.37	14.35	43.59	43.54
E	56	25.52	25.29	50.36	49.78

As can be seen in Figure 2, there is a proportional increase in the mean and standard deviation values of the image with the increase in mAs. This is due the increase in photons emitted in the creation of the image by the use of a greater amount of current product per second (mAs), which correlates with the increase in information in the image.

Although the average values vary little between 33 kV and 35 kV, this indicates that the increase in tube voltage did not cause a significant difference in the average signal intensity within each region of interest (ROI) of the image. This small variation in the average suggests that the 33 kV and 35 kV settings generate images with similar intensity, which may be related to the stability of the equipment in maintaining image contrast at different voltages.

Thus, standard deviation values also showed a very small difference between 33 kV and 35 kV, indicating that intensity variability, i.e., image contrast, was little affected by the voltage change. This stability is beneficial for quality control, as it indicates that the equipment can maintain a similar noise level regardless of the voltage used. Maintaining little variation in the standard deviation averages is important because it helps to ensure the clarity of anatomical structures.

Fig. 2 Calculus of Mean, Standard deviation and mAs

Figure 3 illustrates the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) calculated using Equation (5), based on the mean and standard deviation results obtained in Table 3. This figure highlights the relationship between 33 kV and 35 kV, showing that despite a 6.06% increase, there is no considerable variation between the obtained SNR values.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the voltage increase allowed by Brazilian legislation (a maximum variation of 5%) leads to an increased patient dose without significantly altering the SNR. Hence, accuracy and reproducibility values must be strictly maintained, as the 33 kV setting provides a sufficient dose to form an image of adequate quality for analyzing small structures.

Fig. 3 Signal-Noise ratio

The Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) values are presented in Figure 4, based on the comparison between two visually similar images acquired with different exposure parameters (implicitly dose). It should be noted that the closer the index is to 1, the smaller the difference between the two images, and the closer it is to 0, the greater the difference between them.

Fig. 4 Structural similarity index (SSIM)

Therefore, it can be analyzed that the comparative images A, B, and C exhibit a high degree of similarity. Specifically, for mAs values of 14, 20, and 25, the SSIM remained above 95%. Images D and E, which are more closely related to the increase in mAs of 40 and 56, had a lower similarity value between 90% and 83%.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper addressed the critical importance of image quality in mammography. Special attention was given to radiation protection and the necessity of adhering to strict protocols to ensure the safety of both patients and professionals.

The evaluation of technical parameters, in accordance with IN 92/21 and RDC 611/22, provided insights into how tube voltage (kV) and electrical charge (mAs) directly influence image quality and radiation dose, emphasizing the importance of a careful balance between these factors.

The practical application of measurements with the Piranha RTI multiparametric meter demonstrated its efficiency in analyzing fundamental parameters, contributing to the quantification of tube voltage and mAs variations. It is possible to analyze that increasing the current-time product affects the number of emitted photons and the exposure time, which can lead to images with darker pixels.

Furthermore, the use of computational methods to assess image quality, such as calculating the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) and the Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), provided a more quantitative approach to the analysis and reinforces the importance of accuracy in radiological practice.

By analyzing the resulting images, it is possible to verify the mean, standard deviation, and SNR values did not undergo major changes with the 6.06% increase in tube voltage. These values are within the recommendation of Brazilian legislation, respecting IN 92/21 and RDC 611/22, which establishes a variation of 5% to 10% when compared to the increase in exposure and exposure rate.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank the Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de Minas Gerais (FAPEMIG), Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (CAPES), Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (CNPq) and the Grupo de Imagens Médicas for the financial and technological support provided for the development of this study and work.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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